

IMAGE OF WOMAN IN JANE EYRE'S NOVEL

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ABSTRACT

This article is based on the well-known novel "Jane Eyre" by Charlotte Bronte. This is a novel of the classical era that absorbed all the most tense, depressing moments from the life of protagonist who, having overcome her trials, proved not only to herself but also to her family that she can go to any obstacles to overcome the life path that she experienced would go to any sacrifices in order to protect them even in the most difficult times.

Charlotte Bronte (1816 - 1855) is an English novelist, the eldest of the three Bronte sisters whose novels have become enduring classics of English literature. It is known that she grew in poverty with no sources of dwelling. Their mother died of lung cancer when the children were very young. Successfully, their father, a poor priest, he himself taught them reading, and guided them to read newspaper. She has been suffered of the miserable life. Bronte sisters had spent a childhood in charity school. These experiences offered the available materials for the prospective creation. Jane Eyre is fully appreciated as her masterpiece. The novel was first published in 1847. At the time, Charlotte Bronte wrote books under the pseudonym Correr Belle.

After publication, the book received good reviews and love from readers. William Thackeray, to whom Charlotte

Bronte dedicated her second edition of Jane Eyre, spoke well about the novel. The writer respected his work very much and in places tried to be like him in writing. However, in society, stinging hints began to appear that, perhaps, William Thackeray is the prototype of Mr. Rochester, since the writer's personal life partially coincided with the grief of the main character of the novel, Charlotte Bronte. Our heroine Jane Eyre is an orphan, and is ill-treated at a young age. She strives for her life, and forms a tough character. She learns how to live from her childhood's environment. Also just for her growing experiences, it creates her strong personality, beautiful ideal and wisdom. Jane Eyre is a special image for female generation. She deserves her efforts and makes a life by herself, dares to show her own voice. While reading the novel, the reader will truly make his first attention on

the plot and genre of the novel what events are in question. The main character is full of willpower and spirit, intelligence and integrity, she does not know what awaits her in life and is constantly on the move until she finds her true home

A persistent theme of this novel is the relationship between a man and a woman. The ability to understand each other, forgive and trust your feelings to another is hard work. Two bright personalities have met and each has the right to their opinion. The feeling of love held together Rochester and Jane, they are ready to sacrifice themselves for the happiness of another.

Furthermore, we should pay special attention to the family values of the novel, from childhood she grew up in a boarding house, as the writer herself grew up with religious customs in the family of a priest. Jane never experienced family warmth and loving care, therefore, in such mutual circumstances, she with high self-control and kindness to people, all this turned her into a sympathetic person.

It is a well-known fact of the problem of a woman's social status in society. Jane strives to become a free person. She is not satisfied with the fate of dependence on a man. She wants to achieve a social position in society with her mind, purposefulness - this, like the author of the novel Charlotte Bronte herself, proves that a woman is capable of a lot in her life, that she can manage her life at the same time and cope with financial independence. As an empirical phenomenon, Jane believes in God sincerely, has been observed repeatedly. By this analysis we can conclude that she will never destroy a church-bound marriage, even if she has to give up her feelings for this.

Besides, the main issue of this article is the fate of a genuine woman who fights for her life and her rights, wrapping everyone with her good nature and care. There is no evil or deliberate purpose in it to gain the trust of society. At the sight of this girl, you can find out that the author has deprived her of girlish beauty, on the other side, her actions give her appearance the most beautiful that her true guise is hidden in the soul is the fight against feminism of noble girls deprived of their rights. It is vital to note that feminism appeared in the 30s of the 19th century in the United States. There is no common feminism. There are many different currents of feminism; therefore, when considering the history of feminism, one must consider the different types of movements of women and their allies. Feminist currents often overlap with each other. There were movements that included black and white women, rich and poor, young and old. And all of these movements focused on different issues. As for the novel, Jane is harassed by her society that does not recognize her as a woman, including her distant relatives who took her into custody after the death of her parents. The evidence of this novel suggests a variety of factors related to real life. It has been a strong belief that women always are put under the pressure of government thus man-dominated society. Each of us, no matter who are we, have the rights to pursue happiness, to pursue the true spirit of life, which can be seen from Jane Eyre's struggle for independence and equality.

To make our research more clarified, we should take into consideration that there are people who are not willing to choose and be chosen. By this research we can notice that Bronte has pointed most global problem that was crucial to solve.

The main idea that the author wants to convey to us is that a woman should not depend on a man and indulge him. With great effort and patience, she deserves to achieve everything herself without any reproaches and worries from the man. A woman should strive to remain herself, even in marriage. Even if she and a man have an unequal position in society, she must maintain her dignity and not allow herself to be enslaved. Today, deeply aware of the stereotypes of the past generations, it becomes obvious that women are not only capable of doing household chores all the time, but she is also able to overcome the path leading to a decent salary, based on this, one can notice that women have reached the greatest heights in the field of finance, journalism, academic degrees and many others that show the whole integrity of the female individual.

The given questions and arguments regarding the article remain unresolved, the reason of it is that not in all countries of the world has a symbol of freedom for the female generation, the fate of many women still lies under male influence and under the supervision of the state, but the author certainly writing this novel in order to direct all women to accept the decision, be independent individuals and know their perfection.

Based on the results, it can be concluded that while reading a novel it can be observed the image of a woman that the author wanted to show us: strong in spirit, undeniable persistence and talent to change this world. A woman, despite her external features, is beautiful with her actions, which at the end of the novel lead her to the true fortune

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